

ROLE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS AND IMPORTANCE

Dilafuza Norboeva

Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service of the Department of Uzbek Language
and Literature, Senior lecturer

norboyeva_dilafuz73@gmail.com

Abstract: This article is devoted to the study of the role of professional terminology as one of the ways to modernize education in the development of specialties in the field of tourism and services. The relevance of this work is due to the fact that in modern conditions of training specialists, terminological literacy is of particular importance, since it is special terminology that is a source of obtaining and transferring knowledge, a tool for mastering specialties, a path to mutual understanding and cooperation. Only knowledge of terminology ensures the creation of a new one, therefore, the further development of tourism and service. The author analyzes the existing methods of teaching the professional terminology of future specialists and identifies the most effective teaching method.

Keywords: social psychology, communication, training, mental qualities, innovation process, tourism innovation, communication, communication culture

The correctness and stability of the use of terms in practice is achieved by using terminological dictionaries and standards that establish a strictly unambiguous system of concepts and terms and contribute to the ordering of terminology. Currently at stake is the issue of achieving world standards in the field of education, and the use of different directions and forms of its implementation. As we build a free, democratic society based on a market economy and the formation of students' independent thinking in the educational process has become a global problem of society as a whole.

Thus, innovative technologies are effectively implemented in teaching professional terminology to students of the Samarkand Institute of Economics and

Service in the field of tourism and services. Achieving the assimilation of the criteria of the state educational standard shows a new round of the didactic process. In the professional training of future specialists in the field of tourism and services, special attention should be paid to the development of social and psychological knowledge, communication skills, as well as mastering professional terms not only in

Uzbek, but also in Russian and English. Indeed, any change in the life of a society depends on the language. The language reflects changes, radical reforms, scientific and technological progress, close socio-economic ties with other countries. Today it is impossible to imagine this without the terminology of various fields. Scientists have found that today there are more than 500 main areas and dozens of their main divisions, each of which has its own unique system of terminology. It is no secret that various directions are rapidly developing in Uzbekistan, and the terminological system is also enriched. The terminology of tourism and service plays an important role in the terminological system. Tourism is one of the most promising sectors of the economy of any country. Among the factors that determine the level of its development, the high level of personnel qualifications is also important. Since all changes and innovations in society are primarily reflected in the language, they pose a number of tasks for linguists (2, 23). One of these tasks is the linguistic analysis of travel terms and their translation from Russian into Uzbek. During the course, students can use the “Working Together” technology to master the terms in their specialty. The group is divided into 4 subgroups, in each subgroup 4-5 students should participate. Each subgroup has the same task: to compile a glossary of tourism terminology. Each student in a small group is given a separate task: column 1 shows the terms related to tourism in Uzbek, in column 2 these terms should be described in Uzbek (performed by the student under one number), column 3 should contain the international name. Column 3 contains the Russian translation and column 4 contains the definition of the term in Russian (3, 45).

When implementing this technology, attention is paid to the following: each group should include active and passive students in order for the group to score high points, the passive student tries to listen to the active student and pays special attention to spelling, pronunciation and definition of terms (Uzbek, English and Russian) and memorize. This technology requires collaboration, which means its effectiveness is guaranteed. It is known from observations that the terminological system of a particular language develops mainly through word formation, in the linguistic basis of these languages, changing the lexical meaning of words, linking words based on the internal capabilities of these languages, protecting existing terms. The formation of the tourist terminology of the Russian language is divided into 3 stages:

Step 1. The terms were formed at the expense of lexical units in the common language: a single traveler, an overnight stay, an hour of arrival, an hour of departure, a travel book, a guidebook. At the first stage, 3% of Russian travel terms appeared.

Step 2. The terms "tourist" and "tourism" were mastered from the French language as a result of the development of excursion activities: types of excursions (educational, student, cheap, walking excursion), excursion participants (excursion, excursion), means (tent, tourist excursion, shtromskot, bureau, excursion section) is enriched with terms expressing concepts related to. There is a layer of terms that serve to describe the processes associated with the organization of excursions and trips: excursion and excursion work, Turkish route, planned tourism; tent camp, tourist house, tourist base. It was noted that the terms (25%) were formed due to the internal capabilities of the Russian language. Step 3. At this stage, there have been changes in the structure of terms, on the one hand, the internal system of some terms (planned tourism, trade union tourism) has been lost, on the other hand, the influx of English terms has intensified. Forty-eight percent of the terms used in tourism terminology emerged after the 1990s. Most of them are not mentioned in Russian-language annotated dictionaries. Examples of this: flashmaking, drug tourism, volunteer tourism, rubber surfing, boosterism, club cars, glamping(5, 68).

The results of socio-psychological research show that communication plays a very important role in the activities of professionals in the field of tourism and services. Because they carry out their activities mainly through communication. Communication is commonly understood as the process by which people establish and develop verbal communication with each other based on mutual knowledge, knowledge of technical terms and exchange of ideas.

In our opinion, training in specialties is of great importance in training specialists in the field of tourism and services. This is due to the fact that knowledge and mental development of young people, in turn, create their ability to analyze the results of their activities. Analysis of performance results is a complex thought process that leads to the formation of such stages of the cognitive process in students as judgment, conclusion, comparison, habitual assessment. From the above, it is clear that it is very important to teach students to think for themselves, to be creative. After all, the implementation of such education depends on the experience, skills and abilities of our respected teachers.

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